

Fractional-Order Activation Function for Feed Forward Neural Networks using Conformable Derivative

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Abstract

Feed Forward Neural Networks (FFNN) are one of the most used models of machine learning in literature. In this model, one of important parts is the activation function in each layer. It is recommended to use an activation function that minimizes the error and maximizes generalization performance applying different activation functions. In this paper, conformable definition is considered as new fractional derivative in neural networks. Conformable derivative has some beneficial properties comparing to other fractional derivative definitions. Sigmoid activation which is the most widely used function in neural networks was performed with the conformable derivative method and a different solution with high generalization capacity was proposed for back-propagation.

Key Words:

Conformable derivative, Feed Forward Neural Networks, Activation Function, Fractional-Order

1. INTRODUCTION

Fractional differential calculus has been a classic concept in mathematics. The principles are integration and differentiation of arbitrary fractional order hence it is the generalization of the popular integer calculus. In the literature, Some studies have presented fractional differential calculus as a model that defines much better than traditional integer calculation in some area such as image processing, signal processing, medical imaging, neural networks etc.(Wang et al., 2015; Bao et al., 2018).

Feed Forward Neural Networks (FFNN) are one of the most used models of machine learning in literature. In this model, one of important parts is the activation function in each layer. The activation function is not clear that will be more meaningful and more effective. In general, it is left to the knowledge of the expert to manually select the activation function performed in the applications. Therefore, a comprehensive error methodology is not specified for specified for different activation functions in the configuration parameters of FFNN. It is recommended to use an activation function that minimizes the error and maximizes generalization performance applying

different activation functions. According to best result the activation function is automatically selected instead of manually researching the activation function and the fractional degree of function is determined as training hyperparameter. Sigmoid function is well known and widely used as activation functions.

In the literature, The use of fractional-order derivative approach has increased on fractional-order back propagation neural networks in machine learning. There are several fractional derivative definitions such as Caputo derivative, Riemann-Liouville derivative, Caputo-Fabrizio derivative, conformable derivative etc. Caputo derivative, Riemann-Liouville derivative and Grunvald - Letnikovfractional - order derivative were used for fractional-order derivative approach in neural networks (Wang et al., 2017b; Bao et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017a). In this paper, conformable definition is considered as fractional derivative in neural networks.

Conformable derivative has some beneficial properties comparing to other fractional derivative definitions. For example, conformable derivative of a constant function is zero while this feature is not satisfied in most of the other definitions. Also, conformable derivative allows us to apply the formula of the derivative of product and quotient of two functions and chain rule.

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Figure 1: Simple representation of neural network structure

Figure 2: The mathematical representation of one neuron in network structure

2. MATERIALS and METHODS

2.1. Traditional Back Propagation Neural Network

Back propagation algorithm is the most widely used model proposed in 1986 (Rumelhart et al., 1986). The neural network structure is shown Figure 1. when considering the multi-layers network structure with n, l, m parameters, n denotes the neurons size of input and m denotes the neurons size of output layers, l denotes number of hidden layer.

The mathematical representation of one neuron in neural network structure is shown Figure 2

$$net_j = \sum w_{ij}x_j + \theta_j \quad (1)$$

where w, x, θ represent weight, inputs and bias of neurons respectively. The bias is also called a "pseudo input" to each neuron in the hidden layer and the output layer. It is used when the values of an input are zero. This is critical problem. The network couldn't be trained without a bias because of zero values.

Each unit receives the output of the previous layer and also it is as the input of the next layers. If there are n samples $(x_k, y_k)(k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$. o_i denotes the output of any node, x_k denotes the inputs. y_k is the outputs of the network. o_{ik} is

the output of the node i . If n samples and j nodes in k layer are used the formulation is,

$$net_{jk}^l = \sum w_{ij}^l O_{jk}^{l-1} + \theta_j^{l-1} \quad (2)$$

The output of layers is,

$$O_{jk}^{l-1} = \varphi(net_{jk}^l). \quad (3)$$

where O_{jk}^{l-1} is output of $l-1$ layer

E denotes the output node errors. it is in network can be represented as

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^p \|o_i - t_i\|. \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla E = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_1}, \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_l} \right) \quad (5)$$

Each weight is updated using the increment

$$\Delta w_i = -\gamma \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_i} \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, l, \quad (6)$$

where γ represents a learning constant.

The error of the partial derivative according to a weight w_{ij} is calculated using the chain rule twice:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ij}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} \frac{\partial o_j}{\partial w_{ij}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} \frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} \frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

In the last factor of above formula, only one term in the sum, net_j depends on w_{ij} , so that

$$\frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{ij}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial w_{ij}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n w_{kj} o_k \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial w_{ij}} w_{ij} o_i = o_i. \quad (8)$$

The derivative of the output of neuron j according to its input is the partial derivative of the activation function:

$$\frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} = \frac{\partial \varphi(net_j)}{\partial net_j} \quad (9)$$

which for the logistic activation function case is:

$$\frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial net_j} \varphi(net_j) = \varphi(net_j)(1 - \varphi(net_j)) = o_j(1 - o_j) \quad (10)$$

2.2. Fractional-Order Derivative Theory

Some notations and preliminaries related to conformable derivative are given in this section. Let $\alpha \in (n, n+1]$, and f be an n -differentiable function at t , where $t > 0$. Then the conformable fractional derivative of f of order α is defined as

$$T_\alpha(f)(t) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f^{([\alpha]-1)}(t + \varepsilon t^{([\alpha]-\alpha)}) - f^{([\alpha]-1)}(t)}{\varepsilon} \quad (11)$$

where $\lceil \alpha \rceil$ is the smallest integer greater than or equal to α . As a consequence of Definition 2.2, one can easily show that

$$T_\alpha(f)(t) = t^{(\lceil \alpha \rceil - \alpha)} f^{\lceil \alpha \rceil}(t)$$

where $\alpha \in (n, n + 1]$, and f is $(n + 1)$ differentiable at $t > 0$. Let $\alpha \in (n, n + 1]$ and $f; g$ be α -differentiable at a point $t > 0$. Then

1. $T_\alpha(af + bg) = aT_\alpha(f) + bT_\alpha(g)$, for all $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.
2. $T_\alpha(t^p) = pt^{p-\alpha}$, for all $p \in \mathbb{R}$
3. $T_\alpha(\lambda) = 0$, for all constant functions $f(t) = \lambda$.
4. $T_\alpha(fg) = fT_\alpha(g) + gT_\alpha(f)$.
5. $T_\alpha\left(\frac{f}{g}\right) = \frac{gT_\alpha(f) + fT_\alpha(g)}{g^2}$.

2.3. Fractional-Order Back Propagation Neural Network

In the literature, fractional-order approach is used in many studies for training neural networks. Fractional-order Back Propagation algorithm based on Caputo fractional-order derivative (Chen et al., 2020; Bao et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2017a, 2014), The Riemann-Liouville (Wang et al., 2017a; Bao et al., 2018) and Grunvald-Letnikov fractional-order derivative also used (Wang et al., 2017a; Bao et al., 2018).

2.4. Activation functions

In the literature, there are many activation function types. Activation function is one of the building blocks on Neural Network or deep learning. It is a mathematical function added to each neuron. At first the inputs is fed to the input layer, after linear operation inputs and weights, the activation function is applied to it and the outputs of layer are produced. The functions show that which neurons in each layer will be triggered. Only the neurons with some relevant information are activated in every layer. The main task of the function is to introduce non-linearity in the network. They have an important effect on ability of the NN to converge and the convergence speed as well. Hyperbolic Tangent Hyperbolic Tangent is a popular activation function for NN because it is within the range of $(-1, 1)$ and formulation as below:

The conformable derivative of order α of the sigmoid function is expressed as in the following form

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (12)$$

is given as

$$\sigma^{(\alpha)}(x) = \left(\ln \left(\frac{\sigma(x)}{1 - \sigma(x)} \right) \right)^{(1-\alpha)} \sigma(x)(1 - \sigma(x)) \quad (13)$$

According to Remark 1, the conformable derivative of order α of the sigmoid function is expressed

$$\sigma^{(\alpha)}(x) = x^{1-\alpha} \sigma'(x). \quad (14)$$

Let be $\sigma(x) = a$ in equation (9), then we have

$$a = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}. \quad (15)$$

When equation (12) is solved with respect to a , then we obtain

$$x = \ln \left(\frac{a}{1 - a} \right) \quad (16)$$

and the first derivative of Equation (9) is written as

$$\sigma'(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{(1 + e^{-x})^2} = a(1 - a). \quad (17)$$

When $\sigma(x)$ with a are replaced after Equation (13) and Equation (14) are substituted into Equation (11), we obtain

$$\sigma^{(\alpha)}(x) = \left(\ln \left(\frac{\sigma(x)}{1 - \sigma(x)} \right) \right)^{(1-\alpha)} \sigma(x)(1 - \sigma(x)). \quad (18)$$

This completes the proof. Graphics of the conformable derivatives of the sigmoid function for different values of α is shown in Figure 3.

3. CONCLUSION

Artificial neural networks are one of the most popular machine learning algorithms. Moreover, it has increased its importance especially with the introduction of methods such as deep learning. Popular classifiers of recent years mainly use artificial neural networks in supervised models. Speeding up training, increasing classification performances and developing models with higher generalization capacity is the main focus of today. Generative models that produce different representations are being studied by developing new algorithms on unsupervised layers for different input types. Although these models are proposed they are often use Gradient descent based back propagation algorithms in the last layer.

In the literature, different backpropagation algorithms can be implemented with different optimization techniques. Gradient descent is the most basic and common method used in artificial neural networks to determine how much to change the weight of neurons whose value is calculated as feed-forward. This method is based on the 1st order derivation of the function based on the chain rule in back propagation. In this way, values other than the weight to be updated are eliminated and step-by-step optimization is performed for the model.

The first order derivative performed according to the chain rule as shown in equation 7 has been proposed as fractional in different studies and successful results have been reported. Since the fractional derivative process is a method that has the capacity to derivative fractionally between zero and desired value, significant results can be obtained with more sensitive calculations. In the literature, Caputo derivative, Riemann-Liouville derivative and Grunvald - Letnikov fractional - order derivative were used for fractional-order derivative approach in the back propagation process of artificial neural network models with different activation functions (Wang et al., 2017b; Bao et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017a).

In this study, sigmoid activation which is the most widely used function in ANN was performed with the conformable derivative method and a different solution with high generalization capacity was proposed for back-propagation.

Figure 3: Graphics of the conformable derivatives of the sigmoid function for different values of α

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